

FAILURE OF LAMINATED STRUCTURES WITH STRESS CONCENTRATIONS: USE OF THE FRACTURE CHARACTERISTIC VOLUME

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SUMMARY

In this work, we present a new approach to describe the failure of laminated structures with applied stress gradient. In the case of laminated under homogeneous strain field, conventional failure criteria work well. But it is not the case for structures with stress concentration. We developed a pragmatic approach based on a Fracture Characteristic Volume (FCV) easy to use with a numerical method.

Keywords: structure failure, stress gradient, non local criterion

FAILURE OF LAMINATED STRUCTURES

To describe the mechanical behaviour of composite material, several mechanisms operating on various scales [1] have to be considered, as matrix cracking, fibre/matrix debonding, transverse failure, fibre rupture and delamination. If we focus on the failure of laminates, some phenomena can be neglected. Subject to respect some manufacture conditions, laminated composites show a good resistance to delamination and transverse failure. Furthermore experimental observations let appear that the factor which determine the laminate's failure is fibres fracture. In the most case, fibre rupture has a catastrophic aspect on both the laminate and the structure.

A first model based on Continuum Damage Mechanics (CDM) and local ply scale criteria were used to describe the failure of woven ply laminated structures [2]. This model describes:

- the diffuse damage mechanisms characterised by the formation of small cracks running parallel to the fibres
- the inelastic strain observed under shear loading and
- the effects of the coupling between tension and shear on the evolution of the damage and the inelastic strains.

This first model was implemented in a FEM code [3] and numerical simulations were compared to experimental data for plates with an open hole submitted to tensile loading. We could thus establish, as Whitney and Nuismer [4], that the local criterion used to describe the fibre failure does not work when the stress field is not uniform. Following the work of Isupov and Mikhailov [5], we studied [6] a non local criterion based on the average of the stress on a characteristic length. This criterion predicts with a good accuracy the failure of quasi-isotropic plates with open elliptical holes. Nevertheless, for woven ply laminates in particular, the fracture zone does not look as a surface (the

thickness multiplied by the characteristic length) but more as a volume. We proposed in [7] a non local criterion based on mean quantities over a ply scale characteristic volume, the *Fracture Characteristic Volume* (FCV). The FCV, a cylinder of ply thickness and a few square millimetres section, depends on the meso-structures of the ply and could be determined by performing two tests on structures showing different stress distributions. The FCV criterion and associated local progressive damage model were integrated into the ABAQUS Software and numerical results were compared to experimental data for woven ply laminated structures.

This paper presents the non local approach combined to the behaviour model. An application on various woven ply laminates was carried out. Comparisons between experimental and simulation data performed on plates with notches and saw cuts show the efficiency of this approach, even for structures with very high stress gradients.

1. NON LOCAL APPROACH

In paper [6], it was observed that using a local criterion to describe the ply failure in the fibre direction lead to underestimate the force at failure by a factor of 1.5 in the case of quasi-isotropic plates with an open hole.

In paper [7], we introduced a non local criterion to account for this stress gradient effect. This non local criterion is based on mean quantities over a characteristic volume defined at the ply scale, the *Fracture Characteristic Volume* (FCV). It corresponds to a cylinder of ply thickness and a few square millimetres section. The choice of this FCV instead of the more conventional characteristic length is consistent with the fracture zone observed experimentally. This approach was validated on various laminates made with Carbon/Epoxy balanced woven ply [8]. Experimentation leads to think that this method can be extend to any type of laminate. As an example, we will show in this paper the validity of the non local approach on Glass/Epoxy unbalanced woven ply laminates.

1.1. A ply scale characteristic volume

In order to study any laminate, it was proposed to use a non local criterion, represented in Figure 1, based on a ply scale characteristic volume $V=hS$. h corresponds to the thickness of the ply and the in-plane area S depends on its meso-structure. A circular area was adopted. Circle is the simplest shape to be defined since it is only characterised by its diameter. It does not need the definition of a direction (contrary to a square for example). The relevance of this choice was already showed for balanced woven ply [7,8] and will be justified in this paper for others plies.

Mean quantities (stresses, strains, damage...) can also be calculated over this volume and fracture criteria can be defined. Thus, the simple criterion based on the maximum of stress: $\sigma_{ij} < \sigma_{ij_{max}}$ will be replace by the maximum of the average stress calculated on

the FCV:
$$\bar{\sigma}_{ij} = \frac{1}{V} \int_V \sigma_{ij} \cdot dV \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{\sigma}_{ij} < \sigma_{ij_{max}} .$$

Any criterion can be used, like a criterion of maximum strain / stress / damage, or a more complex criterion as the Tsai criterion.

Fig1.: Non local criterion based on a *Fracture Characteristic Volume (FCV)*

Parameters defining the failure criterion are identified on one or more tests on homogenous specimen. The estimation of the diameter which characterises the circular area S requires only one test on structure, as for example, a tension test on an open hole plate oriented at $[0^\circ]$. The process of identification also need structure computations to compare experimental data to the numerical data. Subsequently, the FCV criterion can be easily applied everywhere in the structure, with any laminate.

1.2. Implementation into the ABAQUS software

The non local criterion based on a *Fracture Characteristic Volume (FCV)* was implemented into the Abaqus Software by using an URDFIL routine. This routine gives access to stresses, strains and internal variables resulting from each step of the incremental calculation. The criterion is computed at each Gauss Point in the structure, from the values of the close Gauss Points included in surface S . The non local criterion we have implemented is slightly enriched since the criterion is tested at points situating at least at a radius (of the circular area S) from the border (see Figure 1).

The size of the mesh has to be smaller than the zone in which the mean quantity is calculated. In paper [8], it was observed that even in the high stress gradient zones, upward of ten Gauss points in the zone, the mean value no longer changes. The computation will be stopped when the FCV criterion will reach for one Gauss Point, if a first ply failure criterion is adopted.

Currently, the integration into the ABAQUS software is limited to plates in tension under static loading conditions but the development to fatigue loading is in progress.

To complete this non local approach, we needed a behaviour model which translates the non linear character of the mechanical behaviour of the laminate. This model, also implemented into the Abaqus Software, is presented in the next paragraph.

2. BEHAVIOUR MODEL OF LAMINATE

A first ply failure model based on a Continuum Damage Mechanics (CDM) was developed for laminated structures in the case of static loading conditions [9]. It rests on the description of the mechanical behaviour of a UD ply [10] and the assumption that a woven ply has the same behaviour than a laminate made with two UD plies. Thus, we are able to model the behaviour of any type of laminate.

2.1. Assumption

The CDM model describes the mechanical behaviour of the material at the ply scale. This meso-model uses thermodynamics expressions in which internal variables are associated to the loss of stiffness. Damage is supposed to be constant in the thickness of the ply.

In order to obtain a general model, the modelled ply is a UD ply. In the case of woven ply, we supposed that the woven ply has the same behaviour than a [0,90] laminate made with two identical UD plies.

2.2. Damageable behaviour of UD ply

In the fibre direction, the UD ply shows linear elastic behaviour when it is submitted to tension loading. In the transverse direction, the behaviour is non linear. Damage appears under the shape of small cracks which run parallel to the fibre direction and leads to a loss of stiffness. When a shear load is applied, decrease of the shear modulus and inelastic strain are observed. The damage kinematics is accounted for in this model by using the three following internal damage variables: the first is the brittle fracture of fibres d_1 , the two others are the decrease of the stiffness under transverse and shear loading, which were denoted d_2 , and d_{12} respectively.

Under tension loading condition, d_1 has to develop suddenly in order to model the brittle behaviour in the fibre directions.

$$d_1=0 \text{ if } (d_2 < 1, d_{12} < 1 \text{ and } Y_{d1} < Y_{1f}) \text{ else } d_1=d_2=d_{12}=1 \quad (1)$$

Y_{1f} is the parameter defining the ultimate force in the fibre direction and

$$Y_{d1} = \frac{\partial E_D^{ps}}{\partial d_1} \frac{\langle \sigma_1 \rangle_+^2}{2E_1^0 (1-d_1)^2} \quad (2)$$

Both gradual developments of damage d_2 and d_{12} depend on the tension load as well as on the shear load and are thus defined:

$$d_2 = \left\langle 1 - e^{-(aY_{d2}^m + bY_{d12}^n - Y_0)} \right\rangle_+ \quad (3)$$

$$d_{12} = c.d_2 \quad (4)$$

with: - Y_o : threshold value of the development of d_2

- a, b, c, m, n : materials parameters

$$- Y_{d_2} = \frac{\partial E_D^{ps}}{\partial d_2} = \frac{\langle \sigma_2 \rangle_+^2}{2E_2^0 (1-d_2)^2} \quad \text{and} \quad Y_{d_{12}} = \frac{\partial E_D^{ps}}{\partial d_{12}} = \frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{2G_{12}^0 (1-d_{12})^2} \quad (5) \text{ et } (6)$$

In the case of unbalanced woven ply reinforced by glass fibres, three tension tests, are necessary to identify all the parameters of the damage model: Y_{1f} is defined from a test on a $[0^\circ]_8$ laminate, a, m and Y_o , from the $[90^\circ]_8$ test, b, c and n from the $[22^\circ]_8$ test.

2.3 Inelastic strain in the shear direction

After loading has been applied to a $[45]_8$ laminate, inelastic strains are observed. These strains may result from the slipping/friction processes occurring between fibres and matrix as the result of the damage. In spite of fibre and transverse directions present inelastic strains under tension load, only the inelastic strains in the shear direction are relevant. We chose a kinematic hardening model to describe these strains.

The coupling between the damage and the plasticity is accounted for with the terms of the effective stress and the effective strain [1,16], which are defined as:

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{12} = \frac{\sigma_{12}}{(1-d_{12})} \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\varepsilon}_{12}^p = \varepsilon_{12}^p (1-d_{12}) \quad (7)$$

It is assumed that stresses σ_1 and σ_2 do not influence the elastic field defined by:

$$f = |\tilde{\sigma}_{12} - X(\tilde{\varepsilon}_{12}^p)| - R_0 \quad (8)$$

where R_0 is the initial inelastic strain threshold and X the hardening parameter.

2.4 Non local failure criterion

Here, instead of using the local force associated to the fibre direction defined by (2), we use the mean value of this force over the volume. We thus replace the criterion (1), which describes the ply failure in the fibre direction, by the following:

$$\bar{Y}_{d_i} = \frac{1}{V} \int_V Y_{d_i} dV \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{Y}_{d_i} < Y_{i_f} \quad (9)$$

If the evolution of the damage is sudden with no plasticity (as the brittle behaviour in the fibre direction), the criterion (9) is equivalent to a mean stress criterion over the volume V .

Finally, two types of failure occur:

(i) Brittle rupture defined by the FCV criterion (9)

(ii) Fracture of the structure by instability due to the localisation of the damage. This instability corresponds to the maximum load on the force / displacement curve.

3. APPLICATIONS

Tension tests were carried out on plates for various laminates made with Glass/Epoxy unbalanced woven ply. Dimensions of the specimens are: 200 x 45 x 2.5 mm. Three geometries were studied:

- plate with an open hole, $\varnothing = 13$ mm
- plate with circular notches on both sides, $\varnothing = 6$ mm
- plate with saw cuts (similar to macro-cracks) on both sides, 3 x 1 mm.

We experimentally observed that the failure of these structures is brittle. The calculations were stopped when the FCV criterion (9) was reached.

In our model, each woven ply is regarded as a $[0^\circ, 90^\circ]$ laminate made with two UD plies. In this case, the failure criterion is evaluated on each “UD ply”. Thus, we had to identify two diameters to define the FCV on the UD ply oriented at $[0^\circ]$ and on the $[90^\circ]$ UD ply. We choose to use tests on open hole plate on $[0^\circ]_8$ and $[90^\circ]_8$ laminates to determine both diameters.

3.1. The non local approach on plates with a hole

Figure 2 gives the comparison between experimental data (—) and the values predicted the CDM model associated to the FCV criterion (-♦-). These results show that the method based on the non linear behaviour and the non local criterion accurately predicted the force at failure and the displacement for a plate with a hole for various types of laminates.

Fig. 2: Comparison between test (—) and numerical (-♦-) data for open hole plates

3.2. Plates with notches and saw cut

We extended the use of the non local criterion in the case of structures which present high stress gradients as plates with macro-crack (corresponding to a saw cut) and circular notches. The force at failure was measured experimentally for various sequences laminates ($[0^\circ]_8$, $[90^\circ]_8$, $(QI)_8$, $[\pm 18^\circ]_{4s}$ and $[15^\circ]_8$) and different stress distributions (plates with a hole, plates with notches and saw cuts on both sides).

The results obtained with the proposed approach (see Figure 3), which combine the local non linear behaviour and the non local criterion (CDM model/FCV), match up the experimental data (Exp) quite well, even for high stress concentrations as it is the case for plates with notches and saw cuts.

Fig. 3: Comparison between simulations and tests for various laminates $[0^\circ]$, $[90^\circ]$, (QI) , $[\pm 18^\circ]$, $[15^\circ]$

4. CONCLUSION

In the model recalled here, diffuse damage and inelastic strain evolution laws were associated with a simple non local ply scale approach based on a *Fracture Characteristic Volume*. In general, this first ply failure model satisfactorily describes the failure of woven ply laminated structures.

This approach was implemented into the ABAQUS Software. This model is able to predict with a relevant precision the failure of different types of laminates in the presence of various singularities, which can generate high stress gradients.

The non-local approach based on the Fracture Characteristic Volume was successfully tested on two different materials: on balance woven ply laminate reinforced by carbon fibres [8] and unbalance woven ply laminate reinforced by glass fibres.

This study concerns only structures in tension. We are still working on compression (material and structure). If necessary, we will consider a difference between tension and compression (in particular in the fibre direction for the FCV).

Finally, the extension of this approach at the case of fatigue loading conditions is in progress.

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